

Supplementary Information #5: “cheat sheets”

Figure 1: Foetus “cheat sheet” showing the average size for humerus and femur at different foetal ages. Once printed at the correct scale, this cheat sheet can be used to quickly assess the age of a foetus bone placed on top of it.

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Figure 2: Foetus “cheat sheet” showing the average size for radius and tibia at different foetal ages. Once printed at the correct scale, this cheat sheet can be used to quickly assess the age of a foetus bone placed on top of it.

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Figure 3: Foetus “cheat sheet” showing the average size for metacarpals and metatarsals at different foetal ages. Once printed at the correct scale, this cheat sheet can be used to quickly assess the age of a foetus bone placed on top of it.